

CHiME-9 Task 1, MCoRec: Multi-Modal Context-aware Recognition

Sean Ackermann, Michael Becker, Erol Celik, Magdalena Eggers,
Johannes Anton Kaiser, Hendrik Leddin, Adrian Nowak, Alexander Reimann,
Dagmar Schöenberg, Johanna Schulze, Alison Vanzetta, Alexandra Wasilkow
South Westphalia University of Applied Sciences (FH Südwestfalen)
Faculty of Computer Science and Natural Sciences
Germany

Abstract—The CHiME-9 MCoRec (Multi-Modal Context-aware Recognition) Challenge targets robust speech processing in real-world, multi-speaker conversational scenarios recorded with distant microphones. It focuses on developing methods capable of handling background noise, overlapping speech, and acoustic variability in everyday environments. This paper presents adaptations to the official baseline system to improve performance across the five challenge (sub)tasks. Our system incorporates targeted optimization of the conversation clustering pipeline, yielding a 14.8% relative improvement in clustering F1. We further refine the audio-visual speech recognition (AVSR) component through systematic parameter optimization of segmentation and decoding, resulting in a 0.9% relative WER reduction. Together, these enhancements deliver a 17.09% relative reduction in the joint ASR-clustering error rate on the development set, highlighting the potential for further model refinement and multimodal integration in future work.

Index Terms—multi-modal speech recognition, conversation clustering, speaker diarization, audio-visual speech recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

The ninth CHiME Challenge introduces the MCoRec task, which aims to push the boundaries of speech recognition in complex, real world conversational settings. The task requires jointly recognizing speech content and associating it with the correct speaker using audio-visual information. Performance is evaluated using a joint ASR-clustering metric, meaning that errors in components such as active speaker detection or conversation clustering can substantially affect the final score, even when standalone automatic speech recognition (ASR) performance remains strong. As a result, system-level performance depends not only on acoustic modeling, but also on the interaction and robustness of multiple pipeline components.

The associated MCoRec dataset consists of single 360-degree audio/video recordings of rooms with multiple simultaneous conversations and high speech overlap, featuring unscripted 6-minute discussions among 2–8 participants organized into groups of 2–4 speakers.

In this work, we present our team’s submission to the CHiME-9 MCoRec challenge, addressing all subtasks of the provided baseline system. Rather than focusing solely on improving standalone ASR Word Error Rate (WER), we investigate how targeted adjustments within the overall pipeline influence the joint ASR-clustering evaluation metric, with

particular attention to components related to conversation clustering.

Our experiments indicate that while modifications to several modules yield only marginal changes in standalone ASR performance, targeted optimization within the clustering pipeline can substantially reduce the joint ASR-clustering error rate. This highlights the importance of component interactions in multimodal conversational systems and motivates a system-level perspective on performance optimization.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the baseline system and methodology. Section III outlines the experimental setup, and Section IV presents the results. Conclusions and directions for future work are given in Section V.

II. METHOD

A. Active Speaker Detection

The optimization approach was to replace the baselines Light-ASD model [1] by the more recent Light-Robust-ASD model [2]. However, despite the better performance in theory, it showed to be slightly worse than the baseline. Thus, this subtask is not considered in our final submission.

B. Face Landmark Detection and Mouth Cropping

In order to optimize the face landmark detection and mouth-cropping video generation pipeline, we explored several approaches. The most promising strategy involved using Google’s MediaPipe model for facial landmark detection, as it provides a significantly higher number of facial landmarks compared to the baseline model and thus was expected to yield more robust results. However, despite an extensive grid search over multiple parameter configurations and the available sessions in the dev-data, none of the tested MediaPipe setups were able to outperform the baseline model on this task.

Since other aspects of improving the baseline showed more promising outcomes we decided to not outline the details in the following sections.

C. Audio-Visual Speech Recognition

For the AVSR component, we employed the AV-HuBERT Cocktail model fine-tuned on the MCoRec training data [3].

III. EXPERIMENTS

During development, we identified that the baseline implementation coupled the *min_duration_off* parameter with *min_duration_on* in the segmentation pipeline. Decoupling these parameters to allow independent tuning initially degraded WER performance. To address this, we conducted a systematic grid search over segmentation parameters to identify optimal values for the modified implementation.

Our optimization focused on three key aspects evaluated on a subset of five development sessions:

- Segmentation parameters: After decoupling, optimized *min_duration_on* (1.0s) and *min_duration_off* (1.2s) to restore and improve performance
- Beam size: Controls the number of hypotheses explored during beam search (evaluated: 4, 8, 12)
- Maximum segment length: Maximum video segment length in seconds (evaluated: 10, 15, 18, 20)

The subset evaluation revealed that the modified segmentation with optimized parameters, combined with beam size 12 and maximum segment length of 20 seconds, provided the best performance. Longer segments (20s vs. 10s) significantly improved results by preserving acoustic context and reducing information loss at segment boundaries. These parameters were then applied to the complete 25-session development set.

We also explored LLM-based post-processing [4] using Qwen3-8B [5] with strict guards to prevent hallucinations. However, evaluation on the complete development set showed no improvement, and this component was excluded from our final submission.

D. Conversation Clustering

Our approach to improving conversation clustering began with the baseline model provided for the challenge. The core of our method is a systematic, multi-stage optimization of the clustering and segmentation parameters to enhance conversation clustering performance, measured by the F1 score per speaker. The initial step involved a modification of the baseline system’s code to decouple the *min_duration_off* parameter from *min_duration_on* of the central ASD chunking parameters. This allowed for independent tuning of the minimum required pause duration between speech segments, which provided an initial improvement in clustering performance. Following this, we focused on the core parameters of the agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithm itself [6]. We performed an optimization of the distance ‘threshold’ and the ‘linkage’ method, which further refined the speaker clusters and improved the F1 score. The most critical step in our methodology was the joint optimization of clustering parameters and the parameters of the upstream Active Speaker Detection (ASD) module. We hypothesized that the quality of the initial speech segmentation is paramount for accurate clustering. Therefore, we included the central ASD chunking parameters — ‘start-threshold’, ‘stop-threshold’, ‘min_duration_on’, and ‘min_duration_off’ — in our optimization search space. This integrated optimization of segmentation and clustering parameters together yielded the most substantial performance increase.

A. ASR Decoding Configuration

Following the decoupling of segmentation parameters (analogous to the clustering pipeline modification described in Section III-B), initial experiments on a five-session development subset evaluated:

- Segmentation parameters: *min_duration_on* \in {0.5, 0.7, 1.0, 1.5}s, *min_duration_off* \in {0.5, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.5}s
- Beam sizes: 4, 8, 12
- Segment lengths: 10, 15, 18, 20 seconds

Key findings from the subset:

- Parameter decoupling required reoptimization; optimal values: *min_duration_on*=1.0s, *min_duration_off*=1.2s
- Segment length of 10s resulted in significantly degraded performance (WER \approx 55%)
- Increasing from 15s to 20s provided consistent improvements
- Beam size increases from 4 to 12 yielded diminishing but measurable gains

Based on these findings, we selected the optimized segmentation parameters with beam size 12 and segment length 20s for evaluation on all 25 development sessions. LLM-based post-processing was explored on earlier system versions but showed no benefit and was excluded from the final implementation.

B. Clustering Experiments

To validate our methods and understand the system’s behavior, we conducted a series of targeted experiments.

To further validate our optimized pipeline and understand the influence of the core components, we conducted a final experiment focusing on the ASD model itself. After achieving our best clustering performance with the original baseline ASD model and a full parameter optimization, we substituted it with an alternative ASD model. This new configuration also underwent the same comprehensive parameter optimization process.

The results showed that while the parameter optimization improved the performance for this alternative model, its best achievable result was still inferior to the peak performance obtained with the original ASD model. This finding highlights that the choice of the ASD model is a critical factor for the clustering task. It suggests that the characteristics of the baseline ASD model are particularly well-suited for this specific clustering pipeline. This serves as an indicator that decoupling the clustering and ASR tasks, potentially by using distinct ASD models or segmentation parameters tailored to each subtask, could be a promising direction for future work.

Second, a parameter sensitivity analysis was performed to understand the individual impact of the ASD segmentation parameters. By varying one parameter at a time while keeping all others at their optimized values, we observed that all four ASD parameters could positively influence the clustering F1 score. The analysis revealed that the ‘start-threshold’ (onset) and ‘stop-threshold’ (offset) for speech detection had a more significant impact on the clustering outcome than

'min_duration_on' (minimum speech segment duration) and 'min_duration_off' (minimum pause duration).

Finally, to quantify the influence of each parameter in the joint optimization, we conducted a feature importance analysis using a Random Forest regressor. The model was trained to predict the clustering F1 score based on the parameter set. The analysis confirmed the findings from the sensitivity analysis, identifying the 'start-threshold' as the most influential parameter on the clustering result.

IV. RESULTS

A. ASR Component Analysis

Table I shows the ASR optimization results on all 25 development sessions.

Table I
ASR PERFORMANCE ON DEVELOPMENT SET (25 SESSIONS)

Configuration	WER	Change
Baseline (coupled segmentation)	0.4987	–
Decoupled, optimized params beam: 12, len: 20s min_duration_on: 1.0 min_duration_off: 1.2	0.4943	-0.9%

The optimized configuration combining decoupled segmentation parameters ($min_duration_on=1.0s$, $min_duration_off=1.2s$) with optimized decoding (beam=12, len=20s) achieved a WER improvement of 0.9% relative to baseline. This modest gain reflects the already strong performance of the fine-tuned AV-HuBERT model.

B. Clustering and Joint ASR-Clustering Performance

Our systematic optimization of the conversation clustering pipeline resulted in significant performance improvements. As illustrated in Figure 1, these gains were achieved incrementally, starting from the baseline and progressively improving with parameter decoupling and optimization. The primary metric for the clustering subtask, the F1 score per speaker, was improved by 14.8% over the baseline system to 0.906. Table II shows the Clustering optimization results on all 25 development sessions.

This enhancement in speaker clustering had a direct positive effect on the overall system performance. The joint ASR-clustering error rate, which penalizes both ASR errors and incorrect speaker attributions, was reduced by 17.09%. This result underscores the importance of accurate speaker clustering for the overall goal. In contrast, modifications to other subtasks by the team did not yield significant improvements in the ASR Word Error Rate (WER), highlighting the clustering module as the main source of our system's performance gain. The findings from our parameter importance analysis, which identified the ASD 'start-threshold' together with the 'segment_min_duration_on' as the most critical parameter, provide a clear direction for future optimization efforts.

Figure 1. The figure shows the stepwise improvement of the per-speaker clustering F1 score. Starting from the baseline, the clustering results are improved by decoupling the parameters. Further improvement is achieved through parameter optimization. The experiment also showed that using alternative ASD models worsened the clustering result compared to the best achievable outcome.

Table II
CLUSTERING PERFORMANCE ON DEVELOPMENT SET (25 SESSIONS)

Configuration	per-speaker F1	Change
Baseline		
"linkage": 'complete'		
"threshold": 0.7		
"onset": 1.0	0.789	–
"offset": 0.8		
"min_duration_on": 1.0		
"min_duration_off": 0.5		
+ Parameter Decoupling	0.837	6.1%
+ Parameter Optimization		
"linkage": 'complete'		
"threshold": 0.85		
"onset": 3.0	0.906	14.8%
"offset": 3.7		
"min_duration_on": 0.7		
"min_duration_off": 1.57		

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we demonstrated that a focused optimization of the conversation clustering module can lead to substantial gains in the overall system evaluation. Our key finding is that the joint optimization of both clustering and upstream Active Speaker Detection (ASD) segmentation parameters is crucial for achieving high-performance speaker clustering. By systematically tuning these parameters, we achieved a 14.8% relative improvement in the clustering F1 score, which in turn contributed to a 17.09% relative reduction in the joint ASR-clustering error rate.

For the ASR component, we addressed the parameter coupling in the baseline segmentation pipeline through systematic decoupling and reoptimization. Through grid-search optimization over segmentation parameters ($min_duration_on$, $min_duration_off$) combined with optimized decoding parameters (beam size 12, segment length 20s), we achieved

a 0.9% relative WER reduction. The successful parameter decoupling and optimization in both ASR and clustering pipelines (analogous to the clustering optimization) underscores the importance of component-specific parameter tuning in multi-task systems.

Our analysis indicates that while all ASD parameters contribute to the improvement, the speech detection 'start-threshold' together with 'segment_min_duration_on' has the most significant impact. A notable observation was that the baseline ASD model, when properly tuned, outperformed a more recent alternative ASD model for the clustering task. This leads us to hypothesize that it may be beneficial to decouple the ASR and clustering pipelines further, potentially employing different ASD models or parameter sets optimized independently for each task. This represents a promising avenue for future research to resolve the differing requirements of ASR and conversation clustering.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank their supervisor, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Stefan Goetze, for his valuable guidance, continuous support, and helpful discussions throughout the course of this research.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Portions of this manuscript were prepared with the assistance of the AI system ChatGPT (OpenAI), specifically used for language editing. The AI output was reviewed and verified by the authors.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This study did not involve human participants, human data, or animals, and therefore did not require ethical approval.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Liao, H. Duan, K. Feng, W. Zhao, Y. Yang, and L. Chen, *A light weight model for active speaker detection*, 2023. arXiv: 2303.04439 [cs.CV]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.04439>.
- [2] J. Liao et al., "LR-ASD: Lightweight and robust network for active speaker detection," *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 133, no. 7, pp. 4749–4769, Jul. 2025, ISSN: 0920-5691. DOI: 10.1007/s11263-025-02399-2. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-025-02399-2>.
- [3] T.-B. Nguyen, N.-Q. Pham, and A. Waibel, "Cocktail-party audio-visual speech recognition," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.02178*, 2025.
- [4] J. H. Yeo, M. Kim, C. W. Kim, S. Petridis, and Y. M. Ro, *Zero-shot audio-visual speech recognition with llms by learning language-agnostic speech representations*, 2025. Accessed: Feb. 5, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2503.06273>.
- [5] Q. Team, *Qwen3 technical report*, 2025. arXiv: 2505.09388 [cs.CL]. Accessed: Feb. 5, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.09388>.
- [6] *Sklearn.cluster.agglomerativeclustering — scikit-learn api reference*. Accessed: Feb. 4, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.cluster.AgglomerativeClustering.html>.